

ULTIMATE STRENGTH PREDICTIONS OF IMPERFECT COMPOSITE PLATES

Qiao Jie Yang and Brian Hayman¹

Department of Mathematics, University of Oslo
P.O. Box 1053 Blindern, Moltke Moes vei 35, NO-0316 Oslo, Norway
Email: qiaojie_norway@hotmail.com, brianha@math.uio.no,
web page: <http://www.uio.no/english>

¹Corresponding author

Keywords: Composite plates, Ultimate strength, Linear material degradation

ABSTRACT

A semi-analytical model for predicting the in-plane compressive ultimate strength of imperfect composite plates has been developed. The model is based on large deflection theory in combination with first order shear deformation theory. After damage initiation, a linear degradation of material properties is applied. A simplified approach is used in which the plate is divided into nine regions and degradation is confined to the affected region of a failed ply. The investigation is performed for both square and long, simply supported plates. The strengths predicted for the square plates with an initial geometric imperfection in a single half sine-wave shape are satisfactory. For the long plates with mixed modes of geometric imperfections, the predicted strengths are acceptable for the thick plates, while the strengths are conservatively estimated for the thin plates. It is believed that the division of the plates has significant influence on the strength predictions. In order to obtain more accurate results, alternative locations of the boundaries between ply regions or increasing the number of ply regions should be considered.

1 INTRODUCTION

Plates made of composites are widely used in many structures such as wind turbine blades and naval ships. In a design situation, the ultimate strength analysis of such structures can be performed by using the nonlinear finite element (FE) method. This approach is widely used and accepted since this can provide results with high accuracy. Much research is reported in the literature regarding this type of analysis. For instance, in order to exploit the full strength of composite plates and shells, the work presented in [1] with application in the aircraft industry and that performed in the network MARSTRUCT [2] with main focus on marine and wind energy applications, aim to develop a more accurate prediction of collapse for composite panels using FE tools such as ABAQUS [3]. Some experimental tests have also been performed in these studies for validation. However, these analyses require special expertise and are normally time consuming in terms of model generation, numerical computation and post-processing. As an alternative, computationally efficient analysis tools using semi-analytical methods for buckling and strength predictions have become common.

Previously, for use in estimating the ultimate strength of stiffened and unstiffened, thin steel plates under in-plane compression, several simplified semi-analytical approaches have been developed by Steen [4] and by Brubak and Hellesland [5,6]. The aim of the present work is to extend these methods to plates made of fibre-reinforced composites having a wide range of thicknesses. The paper presents the strength analysis of simply supported composite plates subjected to uniaxial in-plane compression load using such a semi-analytical method. The method is able to take account of post-buckling deformations, out-of-plane shear deformations, initial geometric imperfections and failure and degradation models for composites. The Hashin and Rotem failure criterion [7] is used to detect the failure in the laminates and the material stiffness reduction is confined to the affected region of a failed ply. Further, to validate the method, the results are compared with the parametric studies conducted by Misirlis using ABAQUS, reported by Hayman *et al.* [2].

2 BOUNDARY CONDITIONS AND DISPLACEMENT FIELD

Figure 1: Plate geometry and load condition.

A rectangular plate is considered, with dimensions $a \times b$ (Figure 1) and an initial out-of-plane deformation w_{init} . The plate is simply supported on all edges and subjected to a mean compression N_x in the x -direction. In the analyses, this is achieved by restraining the edge $x = 0$ in the x -direction and applying a uniform, negative displacement u_c in the x -direction on the edge $x = a$, all four edges being held straight. The total out-of-plane deformation is $w_{tot} = w_{init} + w$. The adopted displacement field is given in Equations (1), and each deformation component is assumed in the form of a truncated double Fourier series [8], the in-plane displacements having in addition a linear component [6,9]:

$$u_0(x, y) = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^M u_{mn} \sin\left(\frac{m\pi x}{a}\right) \cos\left(\frac{n\pi y}{b}\right) + u_c \frac{x}{a} \quad (1a)$$

$$v_0(x, y) = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^M v_{mn} \cos\left(\frac{m\pi x}{a}\right) \sin\left(\frac{n\pi y}{b}\right) + v_c \frac{y}{b} \quad (1b)$$

$$\phi_x(x, y) = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^M x_{mn} \cos\left(\frac{m\pi x}{a}\right) \sin\left(\frac{n\pi y}{b}\right) \quad (1c)$$

$$\phi_y(x, y) = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^M y_{mn} \sin\left(\frac{m\pi x}{a}\right) \cos\left(\frac{n\pi y}{b}\right) \quad (1d)$$

$$\begin{aligned} w_{tot}(x, y) &= w(x, y) + w_{init}(x, y) \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^M w_{mn} \sin\left(\frac{m\pi x}{a}\right) \sin\left(\frac{n\pi y}{b}\right) + \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^M w_{imn} \sin\left(\frac{m\pi x}{a}\right) \sin\left(\frac{n\pi y}{b}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (1e)$$

The symbols u_0 and v_0 represent the mid-plane displacements in the x - and y -directions, respectively. The rotations of a transverse normal about axes parallel to the y and x axes are denoted by ϕ_x and ϕ_y , respectively. The coefficients u_c , v_c , u_{mn} , v_{mn} , x_{mn} , y_{mn} and w_{mn} are unknowns, w_{imn} are given imperfection amplitudes, and m , n , M and N are positive integers.

3 METHODOLOGY

The semi-analytical method is based on large deflection bending theory combined with first order shear deformation theory. The load-displacement response is traced by an incremental procedure, where an arc length parameter is used as a propagation parameter (Figure 2). This method is presented in detail in Yang and Hayman [10,11] and only a brief summary is provided in this section.

Figure 2: Relationship between an arc length parameter increment $\Delta\eta$, a load increment $\Delta\Lambda$ and an incremental displacement amplitude $\Delta\lambda_i$.

Using the Rayleigh-Ritz method and denoting the total potential energy as Π , the incremental form of the stationary potential energy condition for equilibrium is $\delta\dot{\Pi} = 0$, and thus

$$\frac{\partial\dot{\Pi}}{\partial\lambda_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial\eta} \left(\frac{\partial\Pi}{\partial\lambda_i} \right) = C_{ij}\dot{\lambda}_j + F_i\dot{\Lambda} = 0 \quad (2)$$

Here, λ_i represents the displacement and rotation amplitudes, while Λ is the load parameter. A dot above a symbol means differentiation with respect to the arc length parameter η . Further, C_{ij} is a generalised, incremental stiffness matrix and $F_i\dot{\Lambda}$ is a generalised, incremental load vector, where i indicates the row number and j the column number in a matrix. The additional equation required to solve the problem is given by relating the arc length increment parameter $\Delta\eta$ to the load increment $\Delta\Lambda$ and the incremental displacement amplitude $\Delta\lambda_i$:

$$\dot{\Lambda}^2 + \sum_{Displ.} \frac{\dot{\lambda}_i^2}{t^2} + \sum_{Rot.} \dot{\lambda}_i^2 = 1 \quad (3)$$

where t is the plate thickness.

In the propagation process, $\dot{\Lambda}^s$ and $\dot{\lambda}_j^s$ can be determined from Equations (2)-(3) at stage s . The solutions at the next stage ($s + 1$) are then obtained by the first order Taylor series expansion:

$$\lambda_j^{s+1} = \lambda_j^s + \dot{\lambda}_j^s \Delta\eta \quad (4a)$$

$$\Lambda^{s+1} = \Lambda^s + \dot{\Lambda}^s \Delta\eta \quad (4b)$$

The Riks-Wempner iterative procedure [12,13] is applied within each load increment to correct for the disagreement between the external applied forces and the internal forces. A convergence criterion is introduced to determine the number of iterations needed within each load step. This criterion is based on the magnitudes of the unbalanced forces U and the internal forces I [14]:

$$\|U\| < \beta \|I\| \quad (5)$$

In the analyses performed in Section 6, the value of β is set to 0.01.

4 PROGRESSIVE FAILURE MODEL

4.1 Hashin and Rotem Failure Criterion

The Hashin and Rotem failure criterion for in-plane stresses can be written [7]:

$$f_1^T = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_t} \right)^2 = 1 ; f_2^T = \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y_t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{12}} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (6a)$$

$$f_1^C = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_c} \right)^2 = 1 ; f_2^C = \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y_c} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{12}} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (6b)$$

Failure occurs when any of the four failure functions from Equations (6) reaches unity. Each is associated with a dominant failure mode.

4.2 Degradation of Properties

A damaged material stiffness matrix for in-plane deformations is defined [2]:

$$[R] = \begin{bmatrix} (1-d_1)R_{11} & (1-d_1)(1-d_2)R_{12} & 0 \\ \text{sym.} & (1-d_2)R_{22} & 0 \\ \text{sym.} & \text{sym.} & (1-d_6)R_{66} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Here d_1 is the damage factor for the longitudinal direction of the material, d_2 is that for the transverse direction, and d_6 is that for the in-plane shear component. The remaining parameters in Equation (7) are defined as $R_{11} = \frac{E_1}{\Delta}$, $R_{22} = \frac{E_2}{\Delta}$, $R_{12} = \frac{\nu_{12}E_2}{\Delta}$, $R_{66} = G_{12}$ and $\Delta = 1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}(1-d_1)(1-d_2)$.

For the Hashin and Rotem criterion, because the shear failure component is associated with both fibre and matrix modes of failure, the damage variable d_6 is defined as:

$$d_6 = 1 - (1-d_1)(1-d_2) \quad (8)$$

To allow direct comparison with the results of Misirlis [2], the transverse (out-of-plane) shear stiffness matrix is not degraded during the analysis. (The ABAQUS shell elements used by Misirlis did not allow such degradation.) Thus

$$[K] = \begin{bmatrix} K_{44} & 0 \\ 0 & K_{55} \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

where $K_{44} = G_{23}$ and $K_{55} = G_{13}$.

4.3 Material Degradation

For the linear degradation of the material properties, the degradation procedure is based on the constitutive model proposed by Matzenmiller *et al.* [15], i.e. the damage evolution is similar to the model implemented in ABAQUS [3].

5 PLY REGION DEGRADATION MODEL

To use the ply region degradation model (PRDM), first introduced in [16], the plate is divided into 9 regions as shown by the broken lines in Figure 1. Thus regions 1, 3, 7 and 9 are corner regions, 5 is a centre region and 2, 4, 6 and 8 are mid-edge regions (of which 4 and 6 are loaded edges). This division was first introduced in order to enable differentiation between regions having differing predominant stress states. The procedure implemented with linear material degradation and the Riks-Wempner method is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Schematic diagram: the procedure using PRDM with the linear material degradation. The procedure is repeated until the maximum load is reached.

6 PARAMETRIC STUDY

6.1 Description

To validate the simplified approach, the results are compared with those obtained by Misirlis using advanced FE analysis [2]. The parametric studies have been performed for a series of square plates with $a = b = 500$ mm, and long plates with $a = 2000$ mm and $b = 500$ mm. For both square and long plates, various b/t ratios are considered, with initial imperfection amplitudes equal to 0.1%, 1% and 3% of the width b . For the square plates, the shape of the initial geometric imperfection is a single half sine wave. For the long plates, the shape of the initial geometric imperfection is a combination of 20% of the preferred buckling mode shape and 80% of a single half sine wave. Two different types of composite layup are considered as in [2]:

- Case A, a triaxial layup: $[-45 / +45 / 0_4 / +45 / -45 / 0_4 / -45 / +45 / 0_3]_s$

This layup configuration is typical for the main spar of a wind turbine blade.

- Case B, a quasi-isotropic, quadriaxial layup: $[0 / +45 / 90 / -45]_{x,s}$

This layup configuration is more typical for ship hull panels that experience a mixture of lateral pressure and in-plane loading due to hull girder bending.

A plate affine aspect ratio is introduced by Brunelle and Oyibo [17] for determining the preferred buckling mode and establishing generic buckling curves for specially orthotropic plates. This is defined as

$$\frac{a_0}{b_0} = \left(\frac{D_{22}}{D_{11}} \right)^{1/4} \frac{a}{b} \quad (10)$$

Here, a_0/b_0 is the plate affine aspect ratio, and D_{11} and D_{22} are the terms in the bending stiffness matrix corresponding to bending in the x - and y -directions. For simply supported, specially orthotropic plates, Brunelle and Oyibo [17] derived the generic buckling curves shown in Figure 4. This figure also shows the transitions between regions with differing preferred buckling modes. In Figure 4, the affine plate buckling coefficient is given by k_0 and D^* is the generalised rigidity ratio. These are given in Equations (11):

$$k_0 = \frac{N_x b^2}{\pi^2 \sqrt{D_{11} D_{22}}} \quad (11a)$$

$$D^* = \frac{D_{12} + 2D_{66}}{\sqrt{D_{11} D_{22}}} \quad (11b)$$

Here, D_{12} and D_{66} are the in-plane bending coupling term and the twisting term in the bending stiffness matrix, respectively.

Figure 4: Modified uniaxial buckling coefficients vs affine aspect ratio for simply supported plates from Brunelle and Oyibo [17]. Here m is the number of half-waves in the longitudinal direction.

For the layup case A with $a/b = 4$, $D_{22}/D_{11} \approx 0.38$, which implies $a_0/b_0 \approx 3.14$. Thus, the preferred buckling mode for layup case A is three half-sine waves ($m = 3$). For the layup case B, the plate affine aspect ratio is in the range 3.48-3.92, depending on the number of plies. Thus, the preferred buckling mode for the layup case B is four half-sine waves ($m = 4$).

For the triaxial layups (case A), the required b/t values are achieved by scaling the thickness of each individual ply. For the quadriaxial layups (case B), the thickness is increased by adding groups of plies (increasing X) to give the desired b/t values. The material properties and the plate thicknesses for cases A and B are given in Tables 1-2. For the ply region degradation model (see Figure 1) applied for the square plates, regions 1, 3, 7 and 9 are each 160 mm \times 160 mm, regions 2 and 8 are each 180 mm \times 160 mm, regions 4 and 6 are 160 mm \times 180 mm and region 5 is 180 mm \times 180 mm. For the long plates, regions 1, 3, 7 and 9 are each 650 mm \times 160 mm, regions 2 and 8 are each 700 mm \times 160 mm, regions 4 and 6 are 650 mm \times 180 mm and region 5 is 700 mm \times 180 mm.

Property	E_1	E_2	ν_{12}	G_{12}	G_{13}	G_{23}	X_t	X_c	Y_t	Y_c	S_{12}
Value	49627	15430	0.272	4800	4800	4800	968	915	24	118	65
Units	MPa	MPa	-	MPa	MPa	MPa	MPa	MPa	MPa	MPa	MPa

Table 1: Material properties (strengths and moduli).

Layup	b/t	t (mm)	t_0 (mm)	$t_{\pm 45}$ (mm)	Layup	b/t	t (mm)	X	$t_0, t_{\pm 45}, t_{90}$ (mm)
A1	50	10.02	0.39	0.12	B1	62.50	8.00	1	1.00
A2	30	16.70	0.65	0.20	B2	31.25	16.00	2	1.00
A3	20	24.94	0.97	0.30	B3	20.83	24.00	3	1.00
A4	15	33.40	1.30	0.40	B4	15.63	32.00	4	1.00
A5	10	49.98	1.95	0.59	B5	10.42	48.00	6	1.00

Table 2: Plate thicknesses and ply thicknesses for case A layups (left) and case B layups (right).

6.2 Ultimate strength predictions for the square plates

For the square plates, the ratios of the ultimate strengths estimated using the present model to the reference values found by Misirlis using advanced FE analysis are shown graphically in Figures 5 and 6 for layup cases A and B, respectively.

Figure 5: Case A (triaxial layup) with PRDM: the ultimate strengths from the present analyses are compared to the reference values σ_{\max_ref} obtained by Misirlis, for various plate thicknesses t and imperfection amplitudes.

Figure 6: Case B (quadriaxial layup) with PRDM: the ultimate strengths from the present analyses are compared to the reference values σ_{\max_ref} obtained by Misirlis, for various plate thicknesses t and imperfection amplitudes.

For the case A layups, the estimations are in the range 5% higher to 11% lower than ABAQUS results. For the case B layups, the strength predictions are in the range 5% higher to 17% lower than Misirlis's ABAQUS results.

6.3 Ultimate strength predictions for the long plates

The load-end shortening responses without material degradation for the layup cases A1 and B1 in Table 2 with 3% imperfection are provided in Figure 7. In the case of long plates with the combined modes of geometric imperfections, the change in the deformation shape for the thin plate sometimes occurs with a snap-back behaviour that is visible in Figure 7. For the layup cases A1 and B1, the change of the buckling modes occurred at approximately 70 MPa and 35 MPa, respectively. This figure is included to demonstrate that the geometrically nonlinear formulation is fully capable of reproducing such behaviour.

Figure 7: Load vs. end shortening for the layup cases A1 and B1 with 3% imperfection amplitude, elastic responses without material degradation.

For the long plates, the ratios of the ultimate strengths estimated using the present model to the reference values found by Misirlis are shown graphically in Figures 8 and 9 for layup cases A and B, respectively.

Figure 8: Case A (triaxial layup) with PRDM: the ultimate strengths from the present analyses are compared to the reference values σ_{\max_ref} obtained by Misirlis, for various plate thicknesses t and imperfection amplitudes.

Figure 9: Case A (quadriaxial layup) with PRDM: the ultimate strengths from the present analyses are compared to the reference values σ_{\max_ref} obtained by Misirlis, for various plate thicknesses t and imperfection amplitudes.

For the case A layups, the predicted strengths are in the range of 10% higher to 51% lower compared to the ABAQUS results. The greatest discrepancies are observed for the layup case A1. For the case B layups, the estimated strengths are in the range 3% - 68% lower than ABAQUS results. The greatest discrepancies are observed for the layup case B1. In contrast to the layup case A, a trend is observed here: the agreement with the ABAQUS prediction increases with the plate thickness.

Figures 10 and 11 show the deformed shape of the plate after the ultimate load is reached for the layup case A5 with 3% imperfection and the layup case B2 with 1% imperfection, respectively. These figures demonstrate that as the load increases, the shape of the plate deformation becomes closer to the preferred buckling mode shape ($m = 3$ and $m = 4$, respectively).

Figure 10: Layup case A5 with 3% imperfection: (a) the plate shape with the initial geometric imperfection and (b) the deformed shape of the plate after the ultimate load is reached.

Figure 11: Layup case B2 with 1% imperfection: (a) the plate shape with the initial geometric imperfection and (b) the deformed shape of the plate after the ultimate load is reached.

7 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

A semi-analytical method for estimating the in-plane compressive ultimate strength of composite plates has been established. The method takes account of post-buckling deformations, out-of-plane deformations, initial geometric imperfections and failure and degradation models for composites. The plate has been divided into nine regions and the linear material stiffness degradation has been applied to the failed region in a ply. A parametric study has been performed for simply supported square and long plates with aspect ratios $a/b = 1$ and $a/b = 4$, respectively, having a range of thicknesses and geometric imperfections. In order to validate the present model, the strength predictions have been compared with the results conducted by Misirlis using the more advanced FE analysis.

For the square plates, the results obtained are satisfactory. The strengths predicted are in the range of 5% higher to about 15% lower than ABAQUS estimations for all layup cases with a single half sine wave initial geometric imperfection.

For the long plates with a combined initial geometric imperfection, the results achieved are acceptable for the thick plates, while the predictions are too conservative for the thin plates. This could be explained by fact that the plates have been divided into 9 regions in the same way as for square plates; with a long plate a local failure in a ply may be resulting in a reduction of stiffness over an unnecessarily large area. Furthermore, this can lead to an incorrect distribution of stresses in the plate after damage initiation. In contrast, thick plates undergo less bending deformation than thinner plates, so that stresses are more uniformly distributed throughout the plate.

The present nine-region based degradation model can be expected to give satisfactory results for plates having an affine aspect ratio $a_0/b_0 < 1.41$, which ensures that the preferred buckling mode has a single half sine-wave, $m = 1$. This in turn requires an actual aspect ratio $a/b < 1.78$ for layup case A and approximately $a/b < 1.50$ for layup case B. For higher aspect ratios, other locations of the ply region boundaries or an increase in the number of ply regions should be considered in order to provide more accurate strength prediction. Since the shape of the plate deformation follows both the initial imperfection shape and the preferred buckling mode shape, the number of the ply regions could be determined based on these shapes. Since three regions in the axial direction were found to provide satisfactory results for the square plate with a half sine-wave buckling shape, theoretically for long plates having the aspect ratio equal to 4, it is likely that the PRDM should be implemented with approximately 27 and 36 ply regions for the layup cases A (preferred buckling mode with three half sine-waves, $m = 3$) and B (preferred buckling mode with four half sine-waves, $m = 4$), respectively.

It should be mentioned that the model presented in the present paper aims to provide a simplified approach for predicting the ultimate strengths of composite plates, so that increasing the total number of regions would to a large degree defeat the object of using a significantly simpler model than a full

FE analysis. However, in order to compensate for the possible increased number of the ply regions, it may be appropriate to take advantage of symmetry applied at the ply region level for the material degradation. For square plates, because of symmetry, some ply regions have been observed to fail at the same time: 1 and 9, 3 and 7, 4 and 6, 2 and 8. (Region 5 is independent of other regions.) Thus it is only necessary to test the stress state in one region of each pair, and apply the resulting degradation to both regions. It may be possible to apply this kind of symmetry consideration to long plates based on the number of half sine-wave deformation shape. However, it will be necessary to consider carefully the symmetry of the combined imperfection and preferred mode shapes in order to apply such a procedure. This is a topic for further investigation.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. C. Orifici, R. S. Thomson, R. Degenhardt, A. Kling, K. Rohwer and J. Bayandor, Degradation investigation in a postbuckling composite stiffened fuselage panel, *Composite Structures*, 82(2), 2008, pp. 217-224.
- [2] B. Hayman, C. Berggreen, C. Lundsgaard-Larsen, A. Delarche, H. Toftegaard, R. S. Dow, J. Downes, K. Misirlis, N. Tsouvalis and C. Douka, Studies of the buckling of composite plates in compression, *Ships and Offshore Structures*, 6(1-2), 2011, pp. 81-92.
- [3] Dassault Systèmes Simulia Corporation, *Abaqus Documentation Version 6.11*, USA, 2011.
- [4] E. Steen, *Application of the perturbation method to plate buckling problems*, Research Report in Mechanics No. 98-1, University of Oslo, Norway, 1998.
- [5] L. Brubak and J. Hellesland, Strength criteria in semi-analytical, large deflection analysis of stiffened plates in local and global bending, *Thin-walled Structures*, 46(12), 2008, pp. 1382-1390.
- [6] L. Brubak and J. Hellesland, Semi-analytical postbuckling analysis of stiffened imperfect plates with a free or stiffened edge, *Computers and Structures*, 89(17-18), 2011, pp. 1574-1585.
- [7] Z. Hashin and A. Rotem, A fatigue failure criterion for fiber reinforced materials, *Journal of Composite Materials*, 7, 1973, pp. 448-464.
- [8] J. N. Reddy, *Mechanics of laminated composite plates and shells*, 2nd edition, CRC Press, USA, 2004.
- [9] Z. P. Bažant and L. Cedolin, *Stability of structures*, Oxford University Press, USA, 1991.
- [10] Q. J. Yang and B. Hayman, Prediction of post-buckling and ultimate compressive strength of composite plates by semi-analytical methods, *Engineering Structures*, 84, 2015, pp. 42-53.
- [11] Q.J. Yang and B. Hayman, Simplified ultimate strength analysis of compressed composite plates with linear material degradation, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 69, 2015, pp. 13-21.
- [12] E. Riks, An incremental approach to the solution of snapping and buckling problems, *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 15, 1979, pp. 529-551.
- [13] G. A. Wempner, Discrete approximations related to nonlinear theories of solids, *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 7, 1971, pp. 1581-1599.
- [14] M. A. Crisfield, *Non-linear finite element analysis of solids and structures*, Vol. 1, Wiley, England, 1991.
- [15] A. Matzenmiller, J. Lubliner and R. L. Taylor, A constitutive model for anisotropic damage in fiber-composites, *Mechanics of Materials*, 20(2), 1995, pp. 125-152.
- [16] Q.J. Yang, B. Hayman and H. Osnes, Simplified buckling and ultimate strength analysis of composite plates in compression, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 54, 2013, pp. 343-352.
- [17] E. J. Brunelle and G. A. Oyibo, Generic buckling curves for specially orthotropic rectangular plates, *AIAA Journal*, 21(8), 1983, pp. 1150-1156.